

Accounting for friction in cracks under compression and shear in an anisotropic damage model and application to CMCs

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Industrial Context

- Increasing use of ceramic matrix composites for their high temperature specific mechanical performances
- Among others, focus on SiC / SiC composites
 - Aeronautic engine applications
 - Nuclear applications

from [Bernachy-Barbé 2015]

Degradation mechanisms to model

- Crack networks
 - oriented by the fiber architecture... orientations known a priori
 - oriented by the loading direction... orientations unknown a priori
- Crack closure while in compression
- Friction
 - in closed cracks in the matrix
 - in cracked interphases
- Fiber breakage
- Environmental effects, fatigue...
 - may be associated to some part of the crack network [Cluzel 09]

Scientific context

- Need for mechanical macro or meso constitutive models
- Development of damage models coupled with plasticity
 - scalar damage variables [Aubard 94, Hild 96, Maire 98, Gasser 98, Camus 00, Marcin 11]
 - tensorial damage variables
 - 2nd order [Maire 97, Gasser 96, Chaboche 02]
 - 4th order [Ladevèze 02, Cluzel 09]

Initial model (state)

- Anisotropic damage model from [Ladevèze 2002]
 - Compliance tensors are used to let the kinematic completely free
- Damage is split to describe several contributions due to several crack networks

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}} &= \Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_1 + \Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_2 + \Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_m \\ \Delta \dot{\mathbb{Z}} &= \Delta \dot{\mathbb{Z}}_1 + \Delta \dot{\mathbb{Z}}_2 + \Delta \dot{\mathbb{Z}}_m\end{aligned}$$

- Crack closure taken into account in the potential

$$\rho \Psi^{el} = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ : \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ + \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_- : \mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_- + \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \Delta \mathbb{Z} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}$$

Tension

Compression

T/C i.e. Shear

Convexity coming from :

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ &= \mathbb{H}^{-1} : \langle \mathbb{H} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle_+ \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_- &= \mathbb{H}_0^{-1} : \langle \mathbb{H}_0 : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle_-\end{aligned}$$

Initial model (evolution laws)

- Thermodynamical forces

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{Y} &= \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ \mathbb{Y}' &= \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbb{Y}'' = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{R}_{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+) \otimes (\mathbf{R}_{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+)$$

- Evolution laws (only for load driven damage here)

$$z_m(\mathbb{A}) = \left((1 - a) \text{Tr}[\mathbb{A}'^{n+1}] + a \text{Tr}[\mathbb{A}'^{n+1}] \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}}$$

$$\Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_m = \dot{\alpha}_m \frac{(1 - a) \mathbb{Y}'^n + a \text{Tr}[\mathbb{Y}']^n \mathbb{I}}{\bar{z}_m^n}$$

$$\Delta \dot{\mathbb{Z}}_m = \dot{\alpha}_m \frac{b \mathbb{Y}''^n}{\bar{z}_m^n}$$

$$\bar{z}_m(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} z_m(\mathbb{Y}'(\tau))$$

Associated damage direction,
positive dissipated power

Identification

- Complex loading sequence on tubes [Pacou 1996]
 - global increasing tensile loadings to create damage
 - intermediate small amplitude shear and tensile loadings to identify stiffness modifications
 - intermediate proportional loadings to check crack closure and friction

Identification

- Complex loading sequence on tubes [Pacou 1996]
 - intermediate shear loadings at constant tensile loadings to check the relevance of the identification

Recovery of the initial shear stiffness in compression

Equivalent shear behavior identification for null or positive tensile loadings

Limit of the model

Experimental observations on alternate torsion tests

- 2 orthogonal independant crack networks
 - one created during + torsion (+45° normal direction)
 - one created during - torsion (-45° normal direction)

Model limit

- damage description is anisotropic
- damage history is isotropic !
 - maximum level reached in + torsion...

$$\bar{z}_m(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} z_m(\mathbb{Y}'(\tau))$$

$$\Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_m = \dot{\gamma} \frac{\partial z_m}{\partial \mathbb{Y}'}$$

$$f(d_{act}) = d_{act} - \beta_m(z_m)$$

$$d_{act} = Tr[\Delta \mathbb{C}_m]$$

Model evolution

- Follow the work of [Desmorat 2010] on 2nd order damage model
 - introduce an active damage variable as a projection of the state description over the loading direction :

$$d_{act} = \Delta \mathbb{C}_m :: \frac{\mathbb{Y}'}{z_m(\mathbb{Y}')}$$

- the criterion and flow rule remain unchanged :

$$\Delta \dot{\mathbb{C}}_m = \dot{\gamma} \frac{\partial z_m}{\partial \mathbb{Y}'}$$

$$f(d_{act}) = d_{act} - \beta_m(z_m)$$

Validation

- Back to the alternate torsion test
 - identification on the first loading loop i.e. on the first crack network, validation of the damage evolution on the second loop i.e. on the second crack network

From [Bernachy-Barbé 2014]

Accounting for friction

- During compressive / shear loadings, friction can lead to restore completely the stiffness
 - multi-axial testing on CMC tubes [Pacou 96]

- Modeling of friction using a plasticity model [Andrieux 86, Halm 98]
 - infinite friction leads to some difficulties [Chaboche 01]

Case of 1D damage

- Preliminary load : uniaxial damage

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ = \sigma_{nn} \mathbf{V}_{nn}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{C}_m = \alpha_1 \mathbf{V}_{nn} \otimes \mathbf{V}_{nn}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{Z}_m = \alpha_1 \mathbf{W}_{nt} \otimes \mathbf{W}_{nt}$$

- Current load : normal and transverse strain can be easily extracted from damage

$$\sigma_{nn}^2 = \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \Delta \mathbf{C}_m : \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\alpha_1}$$

$$\sigma_{nt}^2 = \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \Delta \mathbf{Z}_m : \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\alpha_1}$$

Case of 1D damage

- Introduction of a kinematic hardening variable R

$$r_{nt} = \mathbf{R} : \mathbf{W}_{nt}$$

- Coulomb's law of friction on crack lips

$$(\sigma_{nt} - r_{nt})^2 - c\sigma_{nn}^2 \leq 0 \quad \text{si } \sigma_{nn} \leq 0$$

$$(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{R}) : \Delta \mathbf{Z}_m : (\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{R}) - c\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \Delta \mathbf{C}_m : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \leq 0$$

- New state potential

$$\rho\Psi = \frac{1}{2}\boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ : \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ + \frac{1}{2}\boldsymbol{\sigma}_- : \mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_- + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{R} : \mathbf{Z} : \mathbf{R}$$

Validation

Compression/torsion tests

- recovery of the initial tensile and shear stiffnesses in compression

Validation

Continuity of the stress/strain evolution for complex loadings

Localization limiter

- Damage models usually exhibit a softening behavior leading to the localization of strains and to mesh dependency [Pijaudier-Cabot, Bazant 1987]. It is the case for the present model if the evolution laws are written in strains [Baranger 2018]
- A localization limiter's aim is to impose an internal length in order to fix (at least) the localization zone and thus to recover a fixed dissipated energy [Pijaudier-Cabot, Bazant 1987, Peerling 1996]
- Localization condition for a gradient based regularization on z

$$0 = \det (n.H.n + l_c^2 \|k\|^2 n.K_s.n)$$

Acoustic tensor
of the non-regularized model

Regularization length

Internal length fixed by the method

Secant stiffness (>0)

Conclusion

- Anisotropic model taking into account
 - non proportional loadings
 - unilateral contact in closed cracks
 - friction in closed cracks under shear
- Validation on the available experimental data
 - complex loading sequences
 - influence of the tensile stress on shear damage evaluation
- Proposition of a localization limiter

Thank you for your attention